

FORMYLATION OF METHYL γ -RESORCYLATE BY GATTERMANN REACTION: SYNTHESIS OF METHYL 2:6-DIHYDROXY-3-FORMYLBENZOATE.

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Methyl γ -resorcyate has been subjected to Gattermann reaction giving methyl 2:6-dihydroxy-3-formylbenzoate, several derivatives of which are studied and the constitution of the ester is established.

Although phenols undergo the usual Gattermann reaction readily, phenolic esters cannot be readily formylated due, no doubt, to the deactivating effect of the carbomethoxy group. Thus methyl β -resorcyate does not undergo the usual Gattermann reaction, but it can only be formylated by Shah and Laiwalla's modified Gattermann reaction using anhydrous aluminium chloride in dry ether (Shah and Laiwalla, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1828).

Methyl γ -resorcyate has now been studied for comparison and it has been found that the formylation proceeds under the usual condition, in absence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The product obtained has been proved to have the structure of methyl 2:6-dihydroxy-3-formylbenzoate (I, R=Me) and has been characterised by the preparation of its 4-nitrophenylhydrazone and semicarbazone derivatives.

The present study thus shows that the carbomethoxy group in the γ -position has no deactivating effect on the reactivity of the resorcinol nucleus, whereas the carbomethoxy group in the β -position has considerable deactivating effect. This is analogous to the difference in the reactivity between the 2-acetyl and 4-acetylresorcinols, the former of which is almost as reactive as resorcinol as regards Pechmann's condensation with ethyl acetoacetate, while the latter is much less reactive. On hydrolysis it affords the corresponding acid (I, R=H), which on decarboxylation gives β -resorcyaldehyde, which establishes the structure of the formyl ester.

The *ortho*-hydroxy-aldehyde structure has been further proved by the formation of coumarin derivatives namely, methyl 7-hydroxy-3-acetylcoumarin-8-carboxylate and ethyl 7-hydroxy-8-carbomethoxycoumarin-3-carboxylate with ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl malonate respectively by the Knoevenagel reaction.

On Clemmensen reduction the formyl ester yields methyl 2:6-dihydroxy-3-methylbenzoate, bromination and nitration of which yields

methyl 2:6-dihydroxy-3-formyl-5-bromobenzoate and methyl 2:6-dihydroxy-3-formyl-5-nitrobenzoate respectively.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Methyl 2:6-Dihydroxy-3-formylbenzoate (I, R=Me).—To a solution of anhydrous methyl γ -resorcyate (3 g., 1 mol.) in dry ether in a flask, cooled by freezing mixture, zinc cyanide (4.2 g., 2 mols.) was added followed by a further addition of dry ether (50 c.c.). Dry hydrogen chloride was then passed for 5 to 6 hours through the cooled solution which was kept well stirred all the time. The zinc cyanide gradually disappeared, the solution turned pinkish and a pasty mass separated.

The ether was decanted and water (50 c.c.) was added to the pasty mass and the mixture was heated on a water-bath for about 2 hours and the mixture filtered hot. The filtrate deposited very long golden yellow needles on cooling, which on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid gave colourless needles, m.p. 113-15°. (Found: C, 55.3; H, 4.6. $C_8H_8O_4$, requires C, 55.1; H, 4.1 per cent).

The experiment was repeated with the addition of anhydrous aluminium chloride in dry ether, when the reaction mixture turned reddish brown and no product could be isolated nor the original γ -ester recovered.

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, prepared as usual, was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in tiny orange needles, m.p. 272-75° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.9. $C_{13}H_{12}O_8N_4$ requires N, 14.9 per cent).

The semicarbazone, prepared as usual, was crystallised from hot alcohol in small needles, m.p. 220-22°. (Found: N, 16.2. $C_{10}H_{11}O_5N_3$ requires N, 16.6 per cent).

Methyl 7-Hydroxy-3-acetylcoumarin-8-carboxylate.—Piperidine (4 drops) was added to a mixture of the formyl ester (1 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (1 g.) dissolved in pyridine (10 c.c.) and the mixture was heated at 100° on a water-bath for 1 hour. The solid, obtained on acidifying with dilute hydrochloric acid, crystallised from hot alcohol in greyish white needles, m.p. 245-46°. (Found: C, 59.4; H, 4.8. $C_{15}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 59.5; H, 4.8 per cent).

Ethyl 7-Hydroxy-8-carbomethoxycoumarin-3-carboxylate.—The formyl ester (1 g.) was condensed with ethyl malonate (1 g.) in the presence of piperidine (4 drops) by heating on a water-bath for 2 hours. The product

obtained on acidification was crystallised from hot alcohol in tiny colourless needles, m.p. 255-56°. (Found : C, 57.0; H, 4.0. $C_{14}H_{12}O_7$, requires C, 57.5; H, 4.1 per cent).

Methyl 2 : 6-Dihydroxy-3-methylbenzoate.—The formyl ester (1 g.), dissolved in hot alcohol (10 c.c.), was gradually added to a mixture of zinc amalgam, prepared from zinc dust (5 g.) according to Robinson and Shah, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1497) and dilute hydrochloric acid (1 : 1, 25 c.c.) at 100°. More alcohol was added whenever necessary to keep the ester in solution. After one hour concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) was added and heating continued for further $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The reaction mixture was extracted with ether. On cooling, the extract left an oil which on being kept in the frigidaire for several days deposited very fine long pink needles, m.p. 62-63°. (Found : C, 64.8; H, 5.6. $C_9H_{10}O_6$, requires C, 65.1; H, 6.0 per cent).

2 : 6-Dihydroxy-3-formylbenzoic Acid (I, R=H).—The formyl ester (0.3 g.) was heated on a boiling water-bath for 2 hours with sodium hydroxide (10 c.c., 10%). The solution was acidified and extracted with ether. The yellow solid left on evaporation of the ether was crystallised from hot water in small pale yellow needles, m.p. 215-16°. (Found : C, 52.3; H, 3.8. $C_8H_6O_6$, requires C, 52.7; H, 3.3 per cent).

Decarboxylation of the acid was carried out by heating the acid (0.3 g.) in a Carius tube with water (10 c.c.) and hydrochloric acid (1 : 1, 1 c.c.) for 8-9 hours at 180-190° when a solid was obtained. This was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from hot alcohol in very pale yellow needles, m.p. 132-34°. Mixed melting point with an authentic specimen of β -resorcylaldehyde was not depressed.

Methyl 2 : 6-Dihydroxy-3-formyl-5-nitrobenzoate.—The formyl ester (0.5 g.) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) and concentrated nitric acid was added with external cooling. The mixture was left overnight and the solid separating was crystallised from hot alcohol in long pale yellow needles, m.p. 148-50°. (Found : N, 5.6. $C_8H_7O_7N$, requires N, 5.8 per cent).

Methyl 2 : 6-Dihydroxy-3-formyl-5-bromobenzoate.—The formyl ester (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid. Bromine (0.5 c.c.) in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) was added with stirring. The product obtained on diluting the solution the next day was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 143-45°. (Found : Br, 28.9. $C_8H_7O_6Br$, requires Br, 29.0 per cent).